

THE EVOLUTION OF CANADIAN ARCTIC POLICIES

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THE EVOLUTION OF CANADIAN ARCTIC POLICIES

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As climate change and geopolitical tensions pose growing threats to the Arctic, we explore how Canada plans to address emerging challenges.

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Introduction

The Arctic is assuming an increasingly central role in the global landscape. In recent years, in addition to the European Union, Russia, China, the United States and Canada have also issued updated Arctic policy documents, demonstrating a growing interest in this area.

Global interest in the Arctic is growing mainly due to the consequences of climate change, which, with the melting of the ice, is changing conditions in the region, with significant effects also on international balances. The progressive melting of sea ice is making new shipping routes and possible new resources accessible, with various opportunities for mining, oil and gas drilling, and fishing.¹ This increasing accessibility is inevitably intensifying competition for resources and increasing geopolitical tensions.²

¹ Istituto Swiss Re, "Climate change, trade and geopolitics – new risks in the Arctic", 14.06.2023

² Huebert, Rob. "Canadian Arctic Sovereignty and Security in a Transforming Circumpolar World", *Foreign Policy for Canada's Tomorrow*, No. 4, Canadian International Council, 2009.

The aim of this paper is to analyse these changes in relation to Canada's Arctic policies, examining Canada's changing vision for the region, starting with the analysis of the Harper government's Arctic policies (2006-2015) and ending with the Trudeau administration's long-term regional action plan, the *Arctic and Northern Policy Framework* (ANPF) of 2019, and the defence policy update, *Our North, Strong and Free* of 2024, to the recent *Arctic Foreign Policy*.

The paper considers the distinctive characteristics of the Canadian Arctic, starting with the geography and identity element, and then examining how climate change is changing the status of the region and amplifying geopolitical tensions. The increasingly consolidated presence of actors such as China and Russia in the region is, in fact, creating new challenges for Canada and its sovereignty.

The ultimate goal is to understand the reasons behind the Canadian government's marked change in Arctic strategy and what this means for the scenario in the Arctic, also in the light of

the renewed Sino-Russian partnership and the inauguration of the new U.S. administration.

The *Arctic Foreign Policy*, announced by Foreign Minister Mélanie Joly on 6 December 2024, represents the element of Canada's change of pace. In the new specific Canadian foreign policy, there are many innovative elements compared to previous ones, but what certainly stands out the most is the decisiveness with which external threats are to be addressed.

Minister Joly's words at the press conference presenting the policy best represent the change in Canadian vision and awareness:

*the Arctic is no longer free from tension.*³

With these words, Canada drastically renews its view of the Arctic, demonstrating a firm stance in a geopolitical context that presents a multitude of pitfalls.

³ Government of Canada, 'Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy', 06.12.2024

Canada in the Arctic

Canada is an Arctic country and the Arctic is an integral part of Canadian identity and national interests.

The Arctic plays a crucial role for Canada due to several interconnected factors.

Its importance is linked to morphological aspects, such as geography and national identity. In recent years, due to climate change, the strategic value of the region has increased significantly. The consequences of climate change have led to a growing interest in new shipping routes and natural resources, heightening geopolitical tensions and raising questions about Canadian sovereignty and security in the Arctic, which also affects the security of the United States and NATO countries.

Geographically, Canada's land surface is approximately 40% Arctic and northern regions, including the Northwest Territories, Nunavut, Yukon, and some

northern areas belonging to other provinces.⁴ This vast area includes approximately 162,000 kilometres of Arctic coastline (equal to 75% of Canada's entire coastal development) and the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, which consisting of 36,563 islands.⁵

Figure 1. "Canada's Northern Regions". Use kindly granted by *Northern Research Policy Contributions to Canadian Arctic Sustainability*.⁶

⁴ Morrison, W.R. 'Canadian Arctic Sovereignty', *The Canadian Encyclopedia*. Historica Canada, 6.02.2006

⁵ Smith, Stephen. "On thin ice: Who "owns" the Arctic?", *Canadian Geographic*, 7.07.2023

⁶ There are various ways to define the Arctic region. The most common definition is the area within the Arctic Circle, which can be defined as the southernmost latitude in the northern hemisphere where the centre of the sun can remain continuously above or below the horizon for 24 hours; this imaginary line encircles the globe at about 66° 34' N. According to the political definition, the Arctic includes the northernmost territories of the eight Arctic states, the members of the Arctic Council: Canada, Denmark (including Greenland and the Faroe Islands), Finland, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Sweden

In addition to its geographical significance, the Canadian Arctic is deeply intertwined with Canada's cultural and historical identity. This region is home to approximately 200,000 people, half of whom are of indigenous origin or belong to indigenous communities, such as Inuit, Métis and First Nations. Their presence testifies to the deep connection with the land and the rich cultural heritage of the peoples who continue to live and preserve their traditions in this land.⁷

The Arctic thus represents a fundamental component of the Canadian national identity: the 'North' is often invoked by Canada in the construction of the idea of nationhood. This region is part of the myth of Canada, helping to define it as a unique northern nation. The key role of the North in the formation of Canadian national identity is widely recognised in both academic literature

and the United States. There are four million people living in the circumpolar Arctic, including about half a million indigenous peoples. From Perrin, Alison; Ljubicic, Gita; Ogden, Aynslie. "Northern Research Policy Contributions to Canadian Arctic Sustainability", *Sustainability*, 2021.

⁷ The Arctic Council. "Canada", *The Arctic Council*, consulted in 2025

and popular culture.⁸ An emblematic example is the national anthem, in which the expression '*The True North strong and free*' is directly quoted, emphasising the deep connection between Canada and its Arctic territory.⁹

In addition to these intrinsic elements that define Canada as a nation, as anticipated, new elements have emerged in recent years that increase the strategic importance of the Arctic.

The Arctic is the epicentre of global warming, and scientific research shows that the region is warming four times faster than the global average.¹⁰ Temperature changes are more pronounced than in any other area of the planet, with an increase of between two and three degrees over the past fifty years. This phenomenon is leading to a drastic reduction in ice sea, both in the winter and summer months, with an average annual rate of loss of

⁸ Williams, Lisa. 'Canada, the Arctic, and Post-National Identity in the Circumpolar World', *The Northern Review*, no. 33, 2011, pp. 115-116.

⁹ Government of Canada, *National Anthem of Canada*, consulted in 2025

¹⁰ 'Climate change in the Arctic', *Norsk Polarinstittut*, consulted in 2025; Ziebarth, Dan. "EU-Sámi Cooperation in Climate Change Adaptation in the Arctic", *The Arctic Institute*, 10.09.2024.

12.9%. If this trend continues, projections indicate that the Arctic could be almost completely ice-free for most summers as early as 2030.¹¹

Figure 2. "Arctic summer ice extent 1970-2100". Use kindly granted by *The Arctic Institute* and Malte Humpert.¹²

The ongoing environmental transformations are attracting the interests of numerous international actors. The main areas of interest in the Arctic concern the strategic opportunities related to the exploitation of both the new sea routes that are opening up and its rich natural resources.

In light of this, for the Canadian government, climate change is a real 'threat multiplier', increasing

¹¹ Perez, Christian. 'Arctic Competition. Part One: Resource Competition in the Arctic', *Foreign Policy*, 13.10.2020.

¹² The Arctic Institute 'Arctic Maps - Visualising the Arctic', *The Arctic Institute Multimedia*, 17.05.2016

national security risks.¹³ The opening of arctic routes is intensifying competition both for control of new trade routes and access to resources, inevitably contributing to increased geopolitical tensions.¹⁴ According to data from the Arctic Council, the number of ships entering the region increased by 37% between 2013 and 2023.¹⁵

The *North Sea Route* (NSR), which runs along the coast of Russian Siberia and connects China to Europe, could divert some of the maritime trade from the Suez Canal. This shipping route plays a strategic role for both Russia's plans and China's ambitions for the Arctic region.

On the other hand, the *Northwest Passage* (NWP) is of particular relevance to Canada's strategy, which claims it as part of its internal waters. However, this

¹³ Syed Raiyan Amir. 'Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy: A Strategic Framework For Navigating Geopolitical Challenges And Environmental Change', *Eurasia Review*, 8.12.2024

¹⁴ Huebert, Rob. "Canadian Arctic Sovereignty and Security in a Transforming Circumpolar World." *Foreign Policy for Canada's Tomorrow, Canadian International Council*, no. 4, 2009.

¹⁵ Plourde, Julie. 'Ship traffic steadily increasing in Canadian Arctic waters, researchers say', *CBC*, 17.12.2024

position is contested by the United States and other nations, which consider it an international passage subject to international maritime law. Although there is a long-standing bilateral agreement between Canada and the United States that provides for mutual notification of naval movements in the region, the growing interest in Arctic shipping, especially from China, has made the issue even more diplomatically sensitive.¹⁶

Figure 3. "Route of the Northwest Passage". Use kindly granted by *Encyclopedia Britannica*.

These routes could significantly reduce shipping times by 30-50% between Asia, Europe and North America.¹⁷ According to more recent forecasts, by 2050, the most efficient route for transporting goods from Asia to the east coast of North America could

cross the Arctic.¹⁸ On the other hand, however, the two main Arctic sea routes, while increasing in transit frequency, especially between North Asia (northern China and Japan) and northern Europe, do not yet represent readily available alternatives.

The extreme climate of the polar latitudes continues to pose a significant challenge, and the costs associated with rights of way and support services remain high, limiting the full exploitation of these routes.

Even the *Transpolar Sea Route* (TSR), considered by China as a strategic opportunity to expand its presence in the Arctic, remains for now a potential route rather than an established reality. The TSR is a shipping route that directly crosses the Arctic Ocean, passing off the northern coast of Russia, and could significantly reduce transit times between Europe and Asia compared to traditional routes. However, it is currently not fully feasible due to extreme weather conditions, varying ice cover and lack of

¹⁶ Syed Raiyan Amir. 'Canada's Arctic'

¹⁷ Friesen, Garth. 'Why Trump Wants Greenland and Canada: Strategic and Economic Goals', *Forbes*, 26.01.2025

¹⁸ Smith, Stephen. "On thin ice: Who "owns" the Arctic?", *Canadian Geographic*, 7.07.2023.

adequate infrastructure along the route.

Figure 4. "Arctic shipping routes". Use kindly granted by *The Arctic Institute* and Malte Humper.¹⁹

The changing physical geography of the Arctic is also making the region increasingly attractive economically, as access to its vast natural resources becomes easier as the ice melts. The region hosts about 13% of the world's oil reserves and almost 30% of global natural gas reserves, as well as a wide variety of critical minerals, including bauxite, nickel, rare earths and iron ore.

These resources are of ever-increasing strategic value in a global economy geared towards the energy transition and the reduction of carbon emissions, for

¹⁹ The Arctic Institute 'Arctic Maps - Visualising the Arctic', *The Arctic Institute Multimedia*, 17.05.2016

which materials such as rare earth elements (REE) are of paramount importance.²⁰ REEs are indispensable for the present and future economy, from renewable energy to the military and aerospace sector, from electric cars to fibre optics, and even today's smartphones.

The fishing industry also offers resources that increase interest in the Arctic, which currently contributes about 10% of the global catch. The movement of many species northwards, resulting from the warming of the Arctic Sea, and the development of Arctic routes open up new possibilities for fish supplies, constituting an important economic resource.²¹

The Canadian Arctic is therefore becoming increasingly important due to these unprecedented

²⁰ REEs, an acronym for *Rare Earth Elements*, are a group of 17 elements belonging to the metal family. More specifically, they are a series of chemical elements that are given this expression not because of their scarce presence on the planet, but because they are difficult to identify as well as being complex to extract and process. From Radice Fossati, Niccolò. 'The battle of the rare earths. Canada tries to end Chinese dominance', *Arctic Observatory*, 22.11.2024

²¹ Perez, Christian. 'Arctic Competition. Part One: Resource Competition in the Arctic', *Foreign Policy*, 13.10.2020.

transformations. The increasing accessibility of Arctic routes and natural resources, with the consequent strengthening of economic interest in the region, has also transformed the regional geopolitical landscape, forcing a rethinking of national security strategies. After three decades of peace and stability following the end of the Cold War, the concept of 'Arctic exceptionalism', traditionally characterised by low tensions and inter-state cooperation, seems to be coming to an end. This model, which focused on dialogue and cooperation between states through forums such as the Arctic Council, has historically promoted the security of Arctic peoples and communities, now appears threatened by new geopolitical dynamics.²²

Traditionally, Ottawa's Arctic policy has developed, since the post-World War II period, within a close partnership with the United States and transatlantic allies, pivoting on institutional ions, international law and diplomacy. However, with the publication of the defence policy document *Strong, Secure, Engaged* in 2017,

²² Klimenko, Ekaterina. 'The Geopolitics Of A Changing Arctic', *SIPRI Background Paper*, 2019, p. 1

Justin Trudeau's government recognised the profound changes taking place in the global landscape and coupled the traditional concept of Arctic exceptionalism with an awareness of renewed strategic competition.²³ The document marked a first significant shift in Canada's official position, noting Moscow's role in the growing international rivalry and highlighting the possible implications on peace and security.²⁴

In the newly emerging geopolitical context, Russia's strategic interests towards the Arctic are becoming increasingly strong. The updates to Russia's 2023 *Foreign Policy Concept* placed an increasing emphasis on the Arctic region, considering it the second most important after the 'near abroad' (Commonwealth of Independent States - CIS).²⁵ Russia's *Arctic*

²³ Government of Canada, 'Strong, Secure, Engaged', *Minister of National Defence*, 2017

²⁴ Borzi, Laura. 'The Canadian Arctic and the war in Ukraine as a multiplier of past vulnerabilities', *Centro Studi Italia Canada*, 7.05.2024

²⁵ *The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation*, 'The Concept of the Foreign Policy of the Russian Federation', *The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation*, No 229, 13.03.2023

Policy 2035 of 2020 already outlined three main objectives: ²⁶

- the protection of Arctic sovereignty, a responsibility assigned to the Russian Armed Forces with the aim of preventing any security threats and strengthening defence capabilities in the region;
- development of the Arctic as a strategic resource due to its economic significance, as the region already contributes 10% of Russia's GDP and 20% of its exports;
- the consolidation of the North Sea Route as a key global transport artery between Europe and Asia, with the introduction of stricter regulations on the transit of foreign ships.

At the political level, Russia aims to reduce the influence of international forums dominated by the western nations, such as the Arctic Council, while remaining open to cooperation, albeit only with countries that respect its sovereign interests.

²⁶ Meade, Julian R. 'Russia's New Arctic Policy 2035: Implications for Great Power Tension Over the Northern Sea Route', *National Intelligence University*, 21.07.2020

Russia's interest in the Arctic is also being joined by China, which, considering itself a '*near-Arctic state*', published its own Arctic strategy document in 2018, outlining an ambitious engagement in various aspects of the region and defining itself as an 'active participant, builder and contributor in Arctic affairs'.²⁷ The main objectives of the Chinese government are active participation in Arctic governance, promotion of scientific research and development of the *Polar Silk Road* to improve shipping routes between Asia and Europe.²⁸ The 'Polar Silk Road' is precisely China's initiative to integrate the Arctic into the *Belt and Road Initiative* (BRI) by exploiting emerging maritime routes.²⁹

China's involvement in Arctic affairs, in particular through its partnership with Russia, reflects its ambitions to secure access to the region's resources and trade

²⁷ The State Council Information Office of the People's Republic of China, 'China's Arctic Policy', 2018

²⁸ Gagaridis, Alexander. "Backgrounder: China's Arctic Strategy", *Geopolitical Monitor*, 25.02.2020; Lamazhapov, Erdem; Stensdal, Iselin; Heggelund, Gørild. "China's Polar Silk Road: Long Game or Failed Strategy?", *The Arctic Institute*, 14.11.2023.

²⁹ Fedrizzi, Enzo. "The Polar Silk Road: from China to Europe via the Arctic", *Geografia Dlive*, 5.02.2019.

routes, without making formal territorial claims or special rights. Over the past ten years, China has invested over ninety billion dollars in the Arctic.³⁰

The partnership with Russia offers China significant legal advantages, in particular with regard to access to Russia's exclusive economic zone (EEZ), which extends 200 nautical miles from its coastline, as stipulated by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS).³¹

In the light, therefore, of the Arctic policies of Russia and China and the developments of recent years, it seems clear that these states pose a threat to Canada and its interests in the region.

³⁰ Gagaridis, Alexander. "Backgrounder: China's Arctic"; Smith, Stephen. "On thin ice: Who 'owns' the Arctic?", *Canadian Geographic*, 7.07.2023

³¹ Graceffo, Antonio. 'China and Russia Arctic Policy Convergence? Shifting Geopolitics in the North', *Geopolitical Monitor*, 14.10.2024

The Harper government's Arctic policies (2006-2015)

The issue of Canada's North was a key component of the electoral platform of the Conservatives in 2005, who believed that sovereignty over the Arctic was in 'crisis'. Stephen Harper, leader of the Conservative Party (later elected Prime Minister in the 2006 federal election), criticised the Liberal government for failing to address this 'crucial issue' and promised that Canada would acquire the military capabilities necessary to defend its sovereignty from external threats.³² To this end, he outlined an appropriation plan for the region that included: the implementation of naval monitoring systems in northern waters, the purchase of new icebreakers, the construction

of a new military and civil deep-water docking facility, the deployment of new aircraft for search, rescue, and surveillance, the establishment of a new military training centre, and increased support for the *Canadian Rangers*, an essential northern defence force.³³ Harper declared that:

*The single most important duty of the federal government is to protect and defend our national sovereignty. [...] It's time to act to defend Canadian sovereignty. A Conservative government will make the military investments needed to secure our borders. [...] You need forces on the ground, ships in the sea, and proper surveillance. And that will be the Conservative approach.*³⁴

In short, Harper's political message emphasised the need for Canadian action, with a focus on strengthening conventional military forces. Following the election of the Conservative government, the approach towards Arctic policy was called 'use it or lose it',

³² Lackenbauer, P. Whitney; Lalonde, Suzanne. "Searching for Common Ground in Evolving Canadian and EU Arctic Strategies." *The European Union and the Arctic*, edited by Nengye Liu et al., Brill, 2017, pp. 13

³³ Harper, Stephen. Harper Stands Up for Arctic Sovereignty, 22.12.2005

³⁴ Ibid.

which dominated the political agenda from 2006 to 2009.³⁵

The conservatives' defence strategy was characterised by the close link between security and sovereignty, as well as the focus on hard power.³⁶ Unlike its predecessors, commitments to invest in military capabilities reinforced the government's emphasis on hard security, rather than human security.³⁷

The prioritisation of Arctic sovereignty reached its zenith with the '*Canada First, Defence Strategy*' of 2008, which emphasised the defence of Canada's territory and sovereignty in the Arctic. The strategy included an increase in defence spending, emphasising that the Canadian Forces must have the capability to exercise

control and defend Canada's sovereignty in the Arctic.³⁸

The rhetoric of 'use it or lose it' disturbed the peoples of the North, including the indigenous peoples, who continued to express concerns about their exclusion from national and international decision-making processes.³⁹ The *Inuit Circumpolar Council* published the '*Circumpolar Inuit Declaration on Sovereignty in the Arctic*' in 2009, which stated that:

*the inextricable linkages between issues of sovereignty and sovereign rights in the Arctic and Inuit self-determination and other rights require states to accept the presence and role of Inuit as partners in the conduct of international relations in the Arctic.*⁴⁰

Even the 2008 *Ilulissat Declaration*,⁴¹ signed by five Arctic coastal states to address issues such as climate change, protection of the marine environment,

³⁵ Lackenbauer, P. Whitney; Lalonde, Suzanne. "Searching for", pp. 13

³⁶ Dolata, Petra. "A New Canada in the Arctic? Arctic Policies under Harper", *Canadian Studies*, no. 78, 2015, pp. 131-154

³⁷ On Harper's early vision, see Dodds, Klaus. "'We are a Northern Country: Stephen Harper and the Canadian Arctic'", Vol. 47, No. 4, *Polar Record*, 2011, pp. 371-374; Dolata, Petra. 'A New', pp. 131-154.

³⁸ Ibid.; Dolata, Petra. "A New", pp. 131-154; Government of Canada, "Canada First Defence Strategy", 2008

³⁹ Lackenbauer, P. Whitney; Lalonde, Suzanne. "Searching for", p. 13

⁴⁰ The Inuit Circumpolar Council, 'Circumpolar Inuit Declaration on Sovereignty in the Arctic', *Circumpolar Inuit*, 2009

⁴¹ Ilulissat is a city in Greenland

maritime safety and the management of emergencies related to the opening of new shipping lanes, drew criticism from indigenous groups, mainly due to the failure to directly consult local populations.

However, precisely as a result of this declaration, the Canadian Conservative government began to reconsider the involvement of indigenous peoples as key actors in Arctic policy, even going so far as to change its position on the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) in 2010,⁴² cancelling its opposition and promising to officially support it as an 'aspirational document'.⁴³

The idea of the importance of increased cooperation was also a central point in *Canada's northern strategy: our north, our heritage, our future* published in 2009. This strategy reinforced the message for an effective partnership both between the federal government and Canadians in the North and between Canada and its neigh-

bours.⁴⁴ The 'use it or lose it' approach gradually began to give way to a vision more oriented towards cooperation with the people of the Arctic. Furthermore, the strategy identified the United States as an 'exceptionally valuable partner in the Arctic', while highlighting opportunities for cooperation with Russia and shared 'common interests' with the European Arctic states.⁴⁵

This change was further consolidated by the 2010 *Statement on Canada's Arctic foreign policy*.⁴⁶ The policy statement reaffirmed Canada's status as an 'Arctic power' and identified sovereignty as the 'number one Arctic foreign policy priority', but at the same time emphasised the 'rules-based' nature of the region.⁴⁷ The overall message outlined a vision for the Arctic as 'a stable, rules-based region with clearly defined boundaries, dynamic economic growth and trade, vibrant north-

⁴² United Nations, 'United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples', 13.09.2007

⁴³ CBC News, 'Canada endorses indigenous rights declaration', CBC, 12.11.2010; Dolata, Petra. "A New", pp. 131-154

⁴⁴ Government of Canada. 'Canada's northern strategy: our north, our heritage, our future', *Indian and Northern Affairs Canada*, 2009

⁴⁵ Lackenbauer, P. Whitney; Lalonde, Suzanne. "Searching for.", p. 14

⁴⁶ Government of Canada, 'Statement on Canada's Arctic foreign policy', 2010

⁴⁷ Dolata, Petra. "A New", pp. 131-154

ern communities and healthy and productive ecosystems'.⁴⁸

The Declaration outlined both a role of 'robust leadership' and a commitment to cooperation. And from 2009, the message focused on hard security gradually faded, while the tone of cooperation with the peoples of the North and regional partners grew stronger. At the same time, without completely abandoning the initial vision, Canada's historic Arctic sovereignty and the country's determination to continue to defend its rights as a sovereign state continued to be upheld.⁴⁹

The move away from the hard security strategy also occurred because, over time, Arctic sovereignty became a less relevant issue for the Canadian public, and Arctic policy lost centrality in the prime minister's agenda. Overall, Canada moved away from the assertive approach that had characterised the period from 2006 to 2009.⁵⁰ An obvious example of this change was when, in 2014, the percentage of

GDP allocated to defence approached 1%, the lowest level in the previous eighty years. Although Harper had repeatedly emphasised the importance of protecting the North, the resources allocated to this objective were progressively reduced in favour of other budgetary needs.⁵¹

Figure 5. “% of GDP in defence spending”. Use kindly granted by *Angus Reid Institute*

⁴⁸ Government of Canada, 'Statement on Canada's Arctic foreign policy', 2010

⁴⁹ Lackenbauer, P. Whitney; Lalonde, Suzanne. "Searching for," pp. 14

⁵⁰ Dolata, Petra. "A New", pp. 131-154

⁵¹ McKercher, Asa; Leah, Sarson. "Dollars and Sense? The Harper Government, Economic Diplomacy, and Canadian Foreign Policy", *International Journal*, Vol. 71, No. 3, 2016, p. 365.

Arctic and Northern Policy Framework (2019)

The *Arctic and Northern Policy Framework* (ANPF) was issued by the Canadian Liberal government of Prime Minister Justin Trudeau on 10 September 2019. The strategy is specifically Arctic policy and is designed to direct Ottawa's actions in the region until 2030. The then Minister for Crown-Indigenous Relations, Carolyn Bennett, described the strategy as a 'roadmap' of spending programmes in the North by the federal government to achieve the new Arctic vision.⁵² The ANPF is still the Canadian framework for Arctic policies.

The document, published by the Department of Crown-Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs, identifies eight priority objectives,

⁵² Brockman, Alex. "Ottawa's new Arctic policy has lofty goals, but few details on how to reach them, critics say", *CBC News*, 11.09.2019

focusing in particular on human security issues and placing special emphasis on health, infrastructure and economic development. The core of the document lies in the need to bridge the gap between the living conditions that separate southern and northern Canadians, in line with the reconciliation process between the government and indigenous communities.⁵³ The *Framework*, as indicated in the opening sentence, broadly outlines how the federal government intends to achieve a:

profound change of direction

(in its relations with the North).⁵⁴ And a confirmation of this objective is the way the document was drafted, which was done through extensive consultations with the Northern governments and indigenous communities.

The new vision was intended to outline a clear departure from the tone of the previous government,

⁵³ Borzi, Laura. 'The Canadian Arctic'.

⁵⁴ Exner-Pirot, Heather. "Canada's new Arctic policy doesn't stick the landing", *Radio Canada International*, 12.09.2019

which ended in 2015, of Conservative Stephen Harper.⁵⁵

Since its publication, however, the ANPF has been the subject of much criticism; many felt that the document did not represent a coherent strategy, or at least that it failed to establish clear parameters to address the serious socio-economic and health indicators related to Canada's North.⁵⁶ Furthermore, the fact that the strategy was promised by the Trudeau government immediately after the 2015 federal election, but was only made public one day before the start of the 2019 election campaign, certainly did not shield the Canadian government from criticism.

But the main criticism levelled at the *Framework* was that it contained a repetition of information already known. Although the federal government's new Arctic strategy envisaged significant changes, with the ambitious goal

of bridging the inequalities between the peoples of northern Canada and the rest of the country, no concrete details were given on how the identified goals could be achieved.⁵⁷

Critics include Arctic expert Rob Huebert, professor of political science at the University of Calgary, who states that:

*what's not being stated here is any idea of how the government is going to address these well-known issues. [...] You can go through the Harper Arctic policies, the Martin Arctic policy, the Mulroney Arctic policies and basically [the Trudeau policy is] saying nothing new.*⁵⁸

Despite Ottawa's proclamations of aid, it became clear that the stated policy strategy did not represent the 'profound change of direction' envisaged by the Trudeau government. On the contrary, the policy framework highlighted well-known problems that Canadians in the North had already identified for years, including climate change, food insecurity, poverty, infrastructure, health

⁵⁵ The Canadian Press, "New federal Arctic policy includes focus on health, environment, infrastructure", *CBC*, 10.09.2019

⁵⁶ Kikkert, Peter; Lackenbauer, P. Whitney. 'Canada's Arctic and Northern Policy Framework', *Arctic Yearbook*, eds. Lassi Heininen, Heather Exner-Pirot, and Justin Barnes (Akureyri: Arctic Portal), 2019: p.4

⁵⁷ Brockman, Alex. 'Ottawa's new', *CBC News*

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

inequalities and housing shortages.

However, despite the lack of concrete details on how the government actually intended to achieve the main goal of making the peoples and communities of the North 'resilient and healthy', the expression of willingness and commitment to reconciliation with indigenous peoples resonates strongly in the document.⁵⁹

Historian Whitney Lackenbauer, an expert on the Canadian Arctic, argues that the most compelling justification for the Government of Canada's call for a 'profound change of direction' lay in the collaborative process between indigenous, territorial and provincial partners that guided the definition of the document's chapters.⁶⁰ The then mayor of Iqaluit, Madeleine Redfern, also shared this view:

the framework speaks to the fact that we need to be more collaborative, more strategic. It's not a strategy per se, other than to say

⁵⁹ Kikkert, Peter; Lackenbauer, P. Whitney. "Canada's Arctic, p.4.

⁶⁰ Ibid.

*we need to actually be working together.*⁶¹

The first and foremost objective identified by the ANPF is to foster the conditions for 'the indigenous peoples of the Canadian Arctic and the North to be resilient and healthy'. This priority is reaffirmed, through a broader vision of reconciliation between peoples that permeates the entire document, in Goal 8:⁶²

*reconciliation supports self-determination and nurtures mutually respectful relationships between Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples.*⁶³

In general, the eight chapters into which the ANPF is divided are:

1. the resilience and health of the northern and indigenous populations of the Canadian Arctic;
2. the strengthening of infrastructure to bridge gaps with other regions of Canada;

⁶¹ Brockman, Alex. 'Ottawa's new', *CBC News*

⁶² Kikkert, Peter; Lackenbauer, P. Whitney. "Canada's Arctic, p.4.

⁶³ Government of Canada, 'Arctic and Northern Policy Framework', *Crown-Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs Canada*, 2019

3. make local and regional economies strong, sustainable, diversified and inclusive;
4. knowledge and understanding to guide decision-making
5. maintaining healthy and resilient Canadian Arctic ecosystems;
6. the international rules-based order in the Arctic to respond effectively to new challenges and opportunities
7. the protection, security and defence of the Canadian Arctic and its people;
8. support self-determination and nurture relations of mutual respect between indigenous and non-indigenous peoples in the reconciliation process.⁶⁴

In addition to these eight chapters, which deal with the priority objectives set by the federal government, the two additional chapters, the 'International Chapter' and the 'Chapter on Safety, Security and Defence' contained in the ANPF, are of particular importance for the purpose of this analysis, as they address the issues of external threats and geopolitical dynamics in the Arctic

⁶⁴ Government of Canada, 'Arctic and Northern Policy Framework'.

region and address how the Canadian government intends to respond to these challenges.

The 'International Chapter' of the ANPF emphasises the importance of maintaining and strengthening international cooperation in the Arctic:

*well known for its high level of international cooperation on a broad range of issues. [...] Despite increased interest in the region from both Arctic and non-Arctic states.*⁶⁵

The chapter supports the Canadian intention to renew multilateral and bilateral cooperation in the Arctic with a vision in line with the idea of Arctic exceptionalism as a paradigm for the region. The Arctic Council is confirmed as the 'pre-eminent forum for Arctic cooperation', complemented by the 'an extensive international legal framework applies to the Arctic Ocean'.⁶⁶

Canada optimistically reaffirmed its commitment to multilateral diplomacy to promote peace and

⁶⁵ Government of Canada, 'Arctic and Northern Policy Framework International chapter', *Crown-Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs Canada*, 2019

⁶⁶ Ibid.

regional stability so that 'Arctic and northern communities to thrive socially, economically and environmentally', while not ignoring the challenges posed by external threats.⁶⁷

NATO is seen as a 'key multilateral forum' to address Arctic challenges, marking a significant change from the previous policy, which feared antagonising Russia. This reflects a more pragmatic approach: the policy commits to 'restart a regular bilateral dialogue on Arctic issues with Russia in key areas'.⁶⁸ Indeed, both countries showed interest in cooperating on common issues in the Arctic, despite the resurgence of strategic competition and diverging interests elsewhere in the world.⁶⁹

This change was also in response to the policy of reconciliation with Canada's indigenous peoples, which, as seen, is a key objective of the strategy. Indeed, Canada was committed to 'enhance the representation and participation of Arctic and northern Canadians in relevant international forums

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

and negotiations', thus strengthening the link between domestic policies of inclusiveness and international geopolitical priorities. The inclusion of indigenous knowledge in scientific and political decision-making was, in fact, another distinguishing feature of the ANPF.⁷⁰

The 'Chapter on Safety, Security and Defence' complements this diplomatic approach by reaffirming Canada's commitment to protecting its sovereignty in the Arctic. Acknowledging the strategic, military and economic importance of the region internationally, the chapter included among its priorities the need to continue to demonstrate Canada's sovereignty, the strengthening of the military presence in the region for the defence of North America, improved domain awareness, enhanced whole-of-society emergency management, and continued engagement with local communities, indigenous groups and international partners.⁷¹ The chapter reaffirmed the contents of Canada's 2017 de-

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Government of Canada, 'Arctic and Northern Policy Framework: Safety, security, and defence chapter', *Crown-Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs Canada*, 2019

fence policy: *Strong, Secure, Engaged*.⁷²

The connection between the 'International Chapter' and the security chapter reinforced the idea that Arctic stability depended not only on military defence, but also on multilateral cooperation and the strengthening of ties between indigenous communities and the rest of the world. In this way, Canada aimed not only to consolidate its sovereignty in the Arctic, but also its role as a leader in an international order, promoting peace, sustainable development and inclusiveness.

The document, even considering recent policies, is still an indispensable guide for the Canadian government.⁷³

⁷² Kikkert, Peter; Lackenbauer, P. Whitney. "Canada's Arctic", pp. 5-6

⁷³ Borzi, Laura. "The Canadian Arctic".

Our North, Strong and Free (2024)

Six years after the adoption of the *Arctic and Northern Policy Framework*, Ottawa has been faced with the need to update its national defence policy to respond to new strategic challenges that have emerged in the region.

In addition to these international developments, there are two main factors that have prompted the updating of Canada's defence policy: internal and external pressures.

The first factor is Canadian citizens' growing perception of geopolitical threats. An Ipsos poll conducted in 2023 found that 75% of Canadians see the need for increased defence spending, believing it essential to strengthen the country's capabilities to protect its territory and ensure national sovereignty.⁷⁴ Another

2024 poll conducted by *Angus Reid* revealed that, compared to 12% ten years earlier, 29% of Canadians consider Canada's military preparedness and global posture as political priorities,⁷⁵ reflecting a growing domestic concern about national security

Figure 6. "To what extent do you agree or disagree...". Use kindly granted by *IPSOS*.

The second factor is the growing external pressure from Canada's allies, particularly within the NATO context. The allies exert pressure on Canada to meet the 2% of GDP target for defence, a commitment achieved over the past ten years by some twenty member countries of the Atlantic Alliance (out of the thirty-two that

14.11.2024; Bricker, Darrell. "More Than Half (56%) of Canadians Consider Canada's Armed Forces to be Old and Antiquated", *Ipsos*, 4.08.2023.

⁷⁵ Brewster, Murray. "Three new polls suggest a growing number of Canadians want more money spent on defence", *CBC News*, 5.05.2024

⁷⁴ Wright, David. "Opinion - Canada's Armed Forces: On the Brink?", *E-International Relations*,

make it up). Added to this is the fact that Canada is one of only two NATO members not to meet the second commitment, namely to allocate at least 20% of the defence budget to military equipment.⁷⁶ This situation was highlighted by Trudeau himself in 2023 (but never confirmed by him), who 'privately told NATO Canada would never meet 2% defence spending target'.⁷⁷

Figure 7. "Defence on the cheap (compared to U.S. and European NATO members)". Use kindly granted by *The Economist*.⁷⁸

Prompted by these pressures, Prime Minister Justin Trudeau and

Defence Minister Bill Blair published *Our North, Strong and Free: A Renewed Vision for Canada's Defence* on 8 April 2024: a document that, highlighting the need for a new national defence capability capable of responding to the new threats posed by climate change, growing global instability and rapid technological advances, factors that affect Canadian security and prosperity, announces⁷⁹ a new total investment in defence spending of C\$8.1 billion over the next five years and C\$73 billion over twenty years.⁸⁰

The document is accompanied by promises from the Trudeau administration that it will take an 'important step' towards achieving the NATO target of 2% of GDP, with the prediction that, thanks to the new investment, Canada's defence spending-to-GDP ratio will rise to 1.76% by 2029-30.⁸¹

There is, however, strong scepticism as to whether this target will actually be met; in particular, the

⁷⁶ Fillingham, Zachary. "Canada Defense Spending: A 'Fire-proof House' under Threat?", *Geopolitical Monitor*, 30.08.2024

⁷⁷ Chase, Steven. 'Trudeau privately told NATO Canada would never meet 2-per-cent defence spending target: report', *The Globe and Mail*, 19.04.2023

⁷⁸ *The Economist*. "Justin Trudeau's dodgy defence promise", *The Economist*, 13.11.2024

⁷⁹ Fillingham, Zachary. 'Canada Defence'

⁸⁰ Government of Canada, 'Our North, Strong and Free: A Renewed Vision for Canada's Defence', *Department of National Defence*, 2024

⁸¹ *Ibid*.

Parliamentary Budget Officer (PBO)⁸² published a report in July 2024 that contradicts the estimates presented in *Our North, Strong and Free*. In this report, the PBO analyses the main points of the document and, assessing the feasibility for Canada to approach the NATO spending target of 2% of GDP, makes a projection no more than 1.42% by 2029-30.⁸³

Figure 8. "NATO defence spending estimates by 2030". Use kindly granted by *Geopolitical Monitor*.⁸⁴

However, the Canadian government's goal is not limited to

reaching the 2% of GDP threshold in defence spending, nor is it reduced to an attempt to mitigate pressure from allies. Rather, the government aims to reverse the progressive weakening of the *Canadian Armed Forces (CAF)*,⁸⁵ consequence of decades of underfunding and budget reductions.⁸⁶

Karen Hogan, Canada's Auditor General in the autumn of 2022, presenting a report to Parliament on 'Arctic Waters Surveillance',⁸⁷ showed that Canada's capacity to monitor the Arctic was still severely lacking. Hogan pointed out that despite government efforts over the past two decades to strengthen infrastructure and security capabilities, Canada lagged behind other powers with interests in the Arctic region.⁸⁸ A cross-departmental report conducted on several ministries, including Defence, Transport, Fisheries and Environment, revealed that:

⁸⁵ The CAF consists of three main divisions: the *Canadian Army* for land operations, the *Royal Canadian Navy* for maritime defence and the *Royal Canadian Air Force* for airspace control.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

⁸⁷ Reports of the Auditor General of Canada to the Parliament of Canada, 'Arctic Waters Surveillance', 2022

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*

⁸² The Parliamentary Budget Officer (PBO) is an independent institution that provides economic and financial analysis to the Canadian Parliament.

⁸³ Fillingham, Zachary. "Canada Defense"; Creighton, Mark; Kho, Albert. 'Update of Canada's Military Expenditure and the NATO.

⁸⁴ Fillingham, Zachary. 'Canada Defence'

The long-standing issues include incomplete surveillance, insufficient data about vessel traffic in Canada's Arctic waters, poor means of sharing information on maritime traffic, and outdated equipment. The renewal of vessels, aircraft, satellites, and infrastructure that support monitoring maritime traffic and responding to safety and security incidents has fallen behind to the point where some will likely cease to operate before they can be replaced. For example, the Canadian Coast Guard and Transport Canada risk losing presence in Arctic waters as their aging icebreakers and patrol aircraft near the end of their service lives.⁸⁹

There is a general consensus in the Canadian political class that the condition of the *Canadian Armed Forces* is precarious.⁹⁰

According to Minister Blair, problems with equipment and infrastructure have contributed to a 'death spiral' in the recruitment of the Canadian Armed Forces, stating that 'over the past three years, more people have left than have entered'.⁹¹ According to

some, this phenomenon has been further aggravated by recent sexual harassment scandals within the military.⁹² The crisis of inappropriate sexual conduct has weighed on the image of the armed forces, with several military leaders accused of abuse or forced to resign from their positions.⁹³ This situation has generated a cloud of distrust that is affecting enlistments in the military, causing a further problem for the Canadian government.

In this context, the most urgent defence policy task appears to be the 'traditional' one, that is the assertion of sovereignty in the Arctic, where the changing physical geography and geopolitical dynamics make an approach that increases the presence, mobility and readiness of the CAF in the region and near the coast urgent.⁹⁴

The vision of the global system articulated by *Our North, Strong*

⁸⁹ Smith, Stephen. 'On thin ice'

⁹⁰ Wright, David. "Opinion - Canada's"

⁹¹ D'Andrea, Aaron. "Canada's military facing 'death spiral' on recruitment, minister says", *Global News*, 7.05.2024

⁹² Wright, David. "Opinion - Canada's"

⁹³ Van Dyk, Spencer. "'Significant increase' in sexual misconduct in the Canadian Armed Forces, Statistics Canada reports", *CTV News*, 05.12.2023; Burke, Ashley; Brewster, Murray. "A military in crisis: Here are the senior leaders embroiled in sexual misconduct cases", *CBC News*, 3.10.2023

⁹⁴ Borzi, Laura. "The Canadian Arctic".

and Free is unequivocally costly. To give some practical examples:

- climate change requires with increasing urgency the construction of new infrastructure, together with new ice-breakers, aircraft and vessels capable of covering the vast Arctic territory;
- global instability will continue to require military assistance from Canada;
- the technological change represented by artificial intelligence and drone warfare represents a profound shift, rendering old platforms obsolete.⁹⁵

The government should therefore resolve these significant vulnerabilities that jeopardise the ability of the CAF and the *North American Aerospace Defence Command* (NORAD) to repel threats to North America.

The policy statement also provides a detailed list of capabilities and platforms to be pursued by the Canadian military to adapt to the changing threat environment, indicating among other measures:

- control and surveillance of submarine and marine spaces with open possibilities for renewal and expansion of the submarine fleet;
- acquisition of more modern and more effective tactical helicopters;
- acquisition of modern surveillance and assault drones;
- creation in the Arctic of operational support hubs with logistical facilities for a larger military presence, for longer periods and capable of acting in a shorter time frame in the more remote areas of the country.⁹⁶

The document clearly and realistically outlines the changes taking place in the global order in real time and proposes in the section on defence, a programme based on:

- the assertion of Canadian sovereignty, focusing on the Arctic;
- the defence of North America (focusing on the renewal of NORAD);

⁹⁵ Fillingham, Zachary. 'Canada Defence'

⁹⁶ Borzi, Laura. 'The Canadian Arctic'.

- the promotion of Canada's global interests and values.⁹⁷

The document shows that the Canadian government has become aware of the need for a larger role in the global scenario, which requires it to respond to the challenge of competition between powers and which essentially translates into the updating of NORAD and a review of Canada's commitment within NATO.

Throughout history, Canadian defence policy has evolved along two complementary channels: on the one hand, bilateral cooperation with the United States through NORAD, and on the other, the consolidation of multi-lateral engagement within NATO. As geopolitical dynamics changed, these two dimensions became progressively intertwined. NATO has identified Russia as the main threat to the security of its members, while China emerges as a revisionist actor, determined to challenge the international order in the space, cyber and maritime domains. This scenario is manifesting itself through an increase in military exercises, increasingly

assertive policy pronouncements and heated competition between the major powers.⁹⁸

In this increasingly dynamic context, Canada assumes a key strategic role: its geographic location configures it as a crucial gateway to the American continent and assigns NORAD the function of a defensive bulwark in the western Arctic, while serving as a link between North America and NATO. The document *Our North, Strong and Free* expresses this renewed awareness, emphasising Ottawa's commitment to strengthening its influence in the global security architecture and effectively adapting to emerging challenges in the Arctic region.⁹⁹

While the document precisely identifies the areas of intervention needed in relation to the evolving global order, the question remains as to whether Canadian governments will be able to effectively address this challenge. In fact, the specific operational measures of *Our North, Strong and Free* lack detail, leaving room for further implementation and

⁹⁷ Government of Canada, 'Our North, Strong and Free'

⁹⁸ Borzi, Laura. 'The Canadian Arctic'.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

adaptation as the geopolitical context evolves.

In general, military strategy was often put on the back burner in Canada,¹⁰⁰ strengthened by the belief of many that they could rely on the country's privileged geopolitical position, protected on all sides by the ocean or by a friendly superpower to the south. According to the liberal politician Raoul Dandurand, who expressed this view around 1924, Canada was a 'fireproof house, far from flammable materials'¹⁰¹ and, as a result, did not actively prepare for threats because they lay far over the horizon.¹⁰²

Figure 9. "Canadian military expenditure as a percentage of GDP". Use kindly granted by War On The Rocks.¹⁰³

In light of the above, the remarks of former Deputy Prime Minister Chrystia Freeland, when in her 2017 statement as Minister of Global Affairs, she announced to Parliament, resonate particularly well:

To rely solely on the U.S. security umbrella would make us a client state. And although we have an incredibly good relationship with our American friends and neighbours, such a dependence would not be in Canada's interest. That is why doing our fair share is clearly necessary. It is why our commitment to NORAD, and to our strategic relationship with the United States, is so critical. It is by pulling our weight in this partnership, and in all our international part-

¹⁰⁰ Bercuson, David J. 'Why Canadians pay little attention to their military', *The Conversation*, 30.08.2018

¹⁰¹ Gibson, Sarah Katherine. "Dreams of a 'fireproof house'", *The Kingston Whig Standard*, 16.10.2013.

¹⁰² Fillingham, Zachary. 'Canada Defence'

¹⁰³ Lagassé, Philippe; Massie, Justin. 'Don't Count on Us: Canada's Military Unreadiness', *War On The Rocks*, 11.04.2024.

*nerships, that we, in fact, have weight.*¹⁰⁴

These words make explicit Canada's 'client' status vis-à-vis the United States. According to Freeland, instead of thinking independently, Canada has followed the lead of London, Washington, the United Nations and NATO. But the old certainties and the rules-based international order are fading fast.

The world described in *Our North, Strong and Free* moves at a time when climate change and Chinese and Russian incursions into the North represent real intrusions into the 'fireproof backyard'. The Canadian government, as highlighted in the document, seems to have realised the urgency of the issue. However, the lack of detailed operational measures and concrete plans casts significant doubt on the effectiveness of Canadian defence in the near future.

¹⁰⁴ Government of Canada. 'Address by Minister Freeland on Canada's foreign policy priorities', *Global Affairs Canada*, 6.06.2017

The change of pace with the Arctic Foreign Policy (2024)

As noted in the previous chapter, the geopolitical instability that has arisen in recent years has generated new challenges, but also new threats, for the Arctic region, especially as nations such as Russia and China have begun to increasingly turn their attention to their military and economic interests in the region.

Numerous events occurred during 2024 that leave little room for different interpretations.

In early October 2024, the Chinese Coast Guard declared that it had entered the Arctic Ocean for the first time, as part of a joint exercise with Russia, launched in September under the name *Ocean-24*.¹⁰⁵ This was a large-

¹⁰⁵ McCarthy, Simone. "China's Coast Guard claims to have entered the Arctic Ocean for the first time as it ramps up security ties with Russia", *CNN*, 3.10.2024

scale naval and air exercise that covered not only the Pacific Ocean, the Mediterranean, the Caspian Sea and the Baltic, but also the Arctic Ocean, involving more than 400 warships, submarines and support vessels, more than 120 aircraft and around 90 thousand military personnel.¹⁰⁶

At the same time, NORAD reported that it had tracked four Russian military aircraft in Alaska's Air Defence Identification Zone (ADIZ).¹⁰⁷ Similar incidents had already occurred in July 2024, when NORAD reported that two Russian and two Chinese bombers had crossed the same zone.¹⁰⁸ Also in the same month, the U.S. Coast Guard spotted several Chinese military vessels operating in the vicinity of the Aleutian Islands, within the U.S. EEZ.¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁶ The Associated Press. "Russia launches massive naval drills with China", *Defence News*, 10.09.2024

¹⁰⁷ Mahadzir, Dzirhan. "U.S. Fighters Intercept Russian Military Intelligence Aircraft Near Alaska, Japan Says Chinese and Russian Military Aircraft Violate Territory", *US Naval Institute News*, 24.10.2024.

¹⁰⁸ US Department of Defense 'Secretary of Defense Lloyd J. Austin III and Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff General Charles "CQ" Brown Jr Hold a Press Conference', 15.07.2024

¹⁰⁹ The Associated Press. "US Coast Guard spots Chinese naval ships off Alaska island", *Military Times*, 11.07.2024

All these events highlight not only the growing strategic convergence between the world's second and third largest armies,¹¹⁰ but also a clear pattern of incursion operations in the Arctic, the Bering Strait and the waters near Alaska.

Figure 10. "North American Air Defensive Zones". Use kindly granted by *Air & Space Forces Magazine*.¹¹¹

The rapprochement between China and Russia, apart from being based on a convergence of geopolitical interests, is linked to the fact that while Beijing is strengthening its role in the Arctic, Moscow is grappling with a severe budget crisis due to the war in Ukraine. Consequently, Russia is increasingly dependent

¹¹⁰ Global Firepower. "2025 Military Strength Ranking", *Global Firepower*, 2025

¹¹¹ Sherman, Jason. 'Forging a SHIELD for the Homeland', *Air & Space Forces Magazine*, 25.01.2021.

on Chinese state and corporate investments for the development of the Arctic region.¹¹² The joint military exercises, conducted by the two countries, are an unmistakable sign of an increasingly entrenched alliance, requiring a timely and strategic response from Canada.¹¹³

According to expert Rob Huebert, the threat of Chinese and Russian aggression is as urgent for Canada as climate change:

*the Arctic is the prime area where destabilization at a global level occurs; this is where it's going to be fought. [...] Geography makes it inevitable. It's not enough, Huebert continues, for Canada to rely on U.S. might and neighbourliness when it comes to Arctic security. Russia is retrofitting military bases and building new ones in its Arctic, and that can't be dismissed by those who say there's no threat of incursion in ours.*¹¹⁴

The detection of Russian-Chinese activity over North America has highlighted the urgency of upgrading NORAD's detection sys-

¹¹² Fife, Robert; Chase, Steven. 'China gains major Arctic foothold as Russia turns to Beijing more, report finds', *The Globe and Mail*, 7.02.2024

¹¹³ Graceffo, Antonio. 'China and Russia Arctic'.

¹¹⁴ Smith, Stephen. 'On thin ice'

tems. Canada and the United States have decided to implement a network of *Arctic over-the-horizon* radars, capable of providing timely and extensive coverage of Arctic areas. This initiative is an integral part of an ambitious NORAD modernisation programme, announced by the Liberal government in 2022, which will run for 20 years and require a total investment of C\$38.6 billion.¹¹⁵ The project aims to strengthen monitoring and defence capabilities, contributing significantly to the security of North America.¹¹⁶

And while the Trudeau government, since taking office in 2015, has always regarded the Arctic primarily as a matter of domestic sovereignty and an area of international cooperation, it is now clear that it can no longer ignore growing external threats. Canada is therefore now faced with a delicate balance between safeguarding its Arctic sovereignty

and the commitment required to deal with global powers.¹¹⁷

With the realisation that previous Canadian defence policies were either not adequate for the changing regional context or had not been implemented effectively, Canada announced on 6 December 2024 the *Arctic Foreign Policy* (AFP), a comprehensive foreign policy aimed at addressing the growing geopolitical challenges in the North. The policy particularly emphasises the concept of national security in response to increasing foreign activities in the Arctic, particularly those with potential dual-use applications, with both scientific and military research purposes, such as China's research initiatives. The AFP clearly testifies to Canadian awareness following the events noted by NORAD:

While the risk of military attack in the North American Arctic remains low, the region represents a geographic vector for traditional and emerging

¹¹⁵ Government of Canada. "NORAD modernisation project timelines", *National Defence*, 2022

¹¹⁶ Humpert, Malte. 'US and Canada to Step up Arctic Capabilities with Over-the-Horizon Radar and Facilities for F35', *High North News*, 27.03.2023.

¹¹⁷ Syed Raiyan Amir. 'Canada's Arctic'

*weapons systems that threaten broader North American and transatlantic security.*¹¹⁸

Canada's Foreign Minister, Mélanie Joly, announced the *Arctic Foreign Policy* at the policy presentation press conference with these words:

we are in a tough world, and we need to be tough in our response.

To continued:

*Competition is growing across the globe, and the Arctic is not immune. Many countries, including non-Arctic states, aspire for a greater role in Arctic affairs. [...] we need a new approach to advance our national interests and to ensure a stable, prosperous and secure Arctic, especially for the Northerners and the Indigenous Peoples who call Arctic home.*¹¹⁹

From the above speech, as well as from the text of the new policy, Canada's determination to

take note of an increasingly complex geopolitical situation clearly emerges. Joly's statement, 'the Arctic is no longer free from tension', undoubtedly represents this new realisation, so much so that several experts have described the policy as an epoch-making turning point.¹²⁰ The policy also emphasises the importance of national and international cooperation to counter external threats, pledging to work with NATO allies and other like-minded Canadian states.

The AFP, considered by the Canadian government as a supplement to the 2019 *Arctic and Northern Policy Framework*, focuses on safeguarding sovereignty and promoting a stable, safe and prosperous Arctic.¹²¹ Bill Blair points out that: 'the *Arctic Foreign Policy* complements our defence policy, *Our North, Strong and Free: A Renewed Vision for Canada's Defence*, which will see us expand our presence in the North'.¹²² The AFP strategy is based on four pillars:

¹¹⁸ Government of Canada, 'Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy'.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

¹²⁰ Syed Raiyan Amir. 'Canada's Arctic'

¹²¹ Ibid.

¹²² Government of Canada, 'Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy'.

- Assertion of sovereignty.
- Pragmatic diplomacy.
- Leadership in Arctic Governance.
- Inclusive diplomacy.

A more detailed analysis of the policy reveals several points that provide a concrete understanding of how Canada intends to move in the Arctic.

The first pillar of the document, which concerns the assertion of Canadian sovereignty, focuses on the modernisation of NORAD and the need to strengthen the Canadian Armed Forces (CAF). A key aspect of this process is the strengthening of the Canadian Rangers, a component of the CAF that plays a crucial role in Canada's northern regions. Described as the 'eyes and ears' of the country, the Rangers are tasked with providing a military presence in the sparsely populated areas of northern Canada, monitoring and protecting vast territories where the presence of other military forces is limited.¹²³

The government's commitment to strengthening Canada's military presence in the Arctic is also seen

in its willingness to invest significantly in improving its maritime defence capabilities. The Royal Canadian Navy (RCN) is a relatively small force, with a fleet consisting mainly of frigates that entered service in the mid-1990s. Most of these units have now reached their service life limit of about thirty years. To ensure that operational capabilities are maintained, the RCN has embarked on a renewal programme that includes the construction of fifteen new destroyers to replace the current frigates.¹²⁴

However, the long lead time required for implementation (the first ship is not expected to enter service until the mid-thirties at the earliest, while the completion of the entire fleet is expected around 2050) raises reasonable concerns about the Navy's ability to maintain an adequate level of operational readiness in the

¹²⁴ Several military capabilities will play a key role in the exercise of Canada's sovereignty in the Arctic and northern waters, including six new Arctic deep-sea patrol vessels; up to 15 new River-class destroyers; 11 new MQ-9B Sky Guardian drones; up to 16 new P-8A Poseidon multi-mission aircraft specialising in anti-submarine and anti-ship warfare; and 88 new F-35° fighter aircraft from Government of Canada, 'Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy'

¹²³ Government of Canada. "Force 2025", 2022

'transition period', that is to say the near future.¹²⁵

In the document *Our North, Strong and Free*, Canada also announced a plan to replace its fleet of old submarines with twelve advanced, conventionally powered vessels designed to operate in Arctic conditions. The first replacement submarine is scheduled to be delivered by 2035.¹²⁶

In addition to the military presence in the Arctic region, the AFP states that it intends to increase and improve the Canadian presence in the inland waters of the Pease, a crucial area for North American security, particularly along the Northwest Passage naval route.

To this end, the Canadian Coast Guard assumes a fundamental role, performing essential tasks

¹²⁵ Wright, David. "Opinion - Canada's"; Tegler, Eric. "The Royal Canadian Navy's Commander Says It Is In a 'Critical State'", *Forbes*, 30.11.2023.

¹²⁶ are also embryonic considerations about the potential acquisition of nuclear-powered submarines (more efficient in reaching depth and speed and theoretically not having to return to the surface to recharge).

From Tae Yeon Eom. 'Canada's New Submarine Project and the Geopolitical Stakes of the Arctic and Indo-Pacific', *APF Canada*, 23.10.2024

for maritime safety, navigation and environmental protection in the Arctic.¹²⁷ Although not having a military function, the Coast Guard is, in fact, called upon to ensure the safety of trade routes and to respond to emergency situations in Arctic waters. To support it in its operations, in 2024 the Canadian government started the procurement of eight new icebreakers, including two polar icebreakers, which will enable the presence of icebreakers in the Arctic all year round.

Figure 11. "Russia has the world's largest icebreaker fleet (Nov. 2022)". Use kindly granted by Statista.¹²⁸

¹²⁷ The Canadian Coast Guard (CCG) is in charge of Search & Rescue (SAR) communication, navigation and transport missions in Canadian waters. It currently operates 119 ships and 22 helicopters, along with a variety of smaller vessels. Government of Canada. "Canadian Coast Guard, consulted in 2025

¹²⁸ This graph represents the number of major icebreakers and patrol vessels capable of operating

To this end, and in response to the continued expansion of Russia's world-leading fleet¹²⁹ and China's significant progress, Canada announced the *Ice Pact* together with the United States and Finland in July 2024. This collaboration is aimed at strengthening shipbuilding capabilities through closer cooperation in the development of polar icebreakers.¹³⁰

The AFP, as a concrete testimony to Canada's commitment to security, points out that by 2030, Canada will have almost tripled its defence spending compared to 2015.

Figure 12. "Department of National Defence's (DND) annual budget". Use kindly granted by *The Canada Files*.¹³¹

Another key element identified by the AFP for strengthening regional cooperation and security is the invitation to allies and partners selected to participate in *Operation NANOOK*.¹³²

The second pillar of the policy, 'pragmatic diplomacy', also testifies to the intention to concretely strengthen its defence, manifested by the expression of willingness to strengthen partnerships with Arctic allies. In particular, the AFP points out that: 'the Canada–United States defence partnership

in the ice as of November 2022. From Fleck, Anna. "Russia Has The World's Largest Icebreaker Fleet", *Statista*, 24.01.2025.

¹²⁹ The Russians are dominant in icebreaker capacity, with a fleet of over thirty diesel-powered icebreakers and only nuclear icebreakers. Russia has already launched three new nuclear-powered icebreakers as part of its 'Project 22220', with two more planned for 2024 and 2026. It has committed to the sixth and seventh ships in the fleet series in 2023, for delivery by the end of the decade. While China is rapidly gaining capacity, having commissioned its fourth polar ship in 2024.

¹³⁰ Kennedy, Mark; Pincus, Rebecca; Moyer, Jason C.; Exner-Pirot, Heather; Larres, Klaus; Parameswaran, Prashanth. "360° View of America's 'ICE Pact' Polar Icebreaker Partnership with Canada and Finland", *Wilson Center*, 16.07.2024.

¹³¹ Lorincz, Tamara. 'Hyper-militarist defence policy update and federal budget put Canada on dangerous warpath', *The Canada Files*, 15.05.2024

¹³² An annual sovereignty and manoeuvre warfare exercise conducted by the Canadian Armed Forces in the Arctic

is essential to maintaining a secure North American homeland', a statement that clearly suggests the importance of NORAD, but above all the Canadian will to resolve the long-standing dispute with the United States in the Beaufort Sea.¹³³ And, given that the border negotiations will inevitably involve the Inuit organisations concerned, the Canadian government's commitment to the empowerment of indigenous peoples is also emphasised.

In addition to its partnership with the United States, Canada aims to strengthen cooperation with its Arctic neighbours: the Kingdom of Denmark (consisting of Denmark, Greenland and the Faroe Islands), Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden. With this cooperation in mind, the policy establishes new consulates in Anchorage, Alaska, and Nuuk, Greenland.

The AFP also places particular emphasis on pragmatic diplomacy and cooperation with non-Arctic states in the North Atlantic and

North Pacific regions, directly citing nations such as South Korea and Japan as ideal partners.

In the third pillar of the policy, aimed at strengthening its 'leadership in Arctic governance', Canada emphasises the fundamental role it played, together with indigenous peoples, in maintaining the Arctic Council and its importance as an essential tool for cooperation in the region. The AFP highlights how the Council's initiatives have produced enormous benefits for the Arctic and its communities, which could be at risk of being disadvantaged by Moscow's choices. In asserting its leadership, Canada will therefore continue to support the Council as a space for collaboration. Adopting a balanced approach between sovereignty and international cooperation, Arctic foreign policy seeks to strengthen coordination with allies and prioritise Arctic security within existing frameworks.¹³⁴

The fourth and final pillar of the policy, 'inclusive diplomacy', is aimed at supporting the indige-

¹³³ The area in question lies north of the Yukon and Alaska and measures approximately 270,000 square kilometres. Both countries claim jurisdiction over the disputed region through various legal interpretations of the 1825 treaty between Russia and Great Britain.

¹³⁴ Eurasia Group. "Top Risks 2025: Implications for Canada", *Eurasia Group*, consulted in 2025

nous peoples of the North, whose leadership is considered an integral part of policy decisions. Among the actions identified, the AFP establishes the role of Arctic ambassador, which, as stated by Minister Joly will be filled by a person of indigenous origin. The AFP also promotes various policies of empowerment and active involvement of natives in international decision-making. By investing the indigenous peoples with a central responsibility in the realisation of national goals, the Canadian government shows a willingness to conciliate with the natives in order to put up a united front in the face of external threats. Indigenous peoples are thus 'spurred on' by the new policy to play a considerable role and achieve concrete results in the national strategic framework.

In the context of the reconciliation process, the AFP also pays special attention to investments in infrastructure, thus being a catalyst for targeted investments that can foster the development of the necessary infrastructure and bring concrete benefits to the people of the North.

In conclusion, the *Arctic Foreign Policy* represents a much-needed measure for Canada's security and geopolitical strategy, the implementation of which is equally essential. In addition to the risks already identified, mainly related to the growing presence of Moscow and Beijing in the region, there is now added pressure from the new Trump administration¹³⁵ on the Canadian government to increase defence spending; an issue that had already caused great concern during his first term.¹³⁶

In general, President Trump's actions and statements have generated confusion and concern in Canada. Rob Huebert argues that:

*events are moving so quickly that it is difficult to fully understand the ramifications of his words and actions thus far.*¹³⁷

Firstly, Trump has made statements questioning Canadian

¹³⁵ Ibid.

¹³⁶ Gray, Andrew. 'Europe and Canada increased defence spending by 20% in 2024, says NATO', *Market Sreener*, 07.02.2025

¹³⁷ Huebert, Rob; Lagassé, Philippe. 'Strategic Outlook: Canada In Dangerous Times', *Conference of Defence Associations Institute*, 2025, pp. 4-6

independence.¹³⁸ Moreover, he has taken steps to undermine Canada's economic security, either through the threat of imposing harsh tariffs or through the actual enforcement of such measures. The U.S. President appears determined to influence Canadian policies on a wide range of issues, including border control and drug trafficking (such as fentanyl).¹³⁹

Huebert argues that:

*the strength and durability of the Canada-U.S. security relationship is now under the most significant threat that it has faced since before the Second World War.*¹⁴⁰

This 'U.S. threat' makes the implementation of a clear and well-defined strategy all the more urgent.

In parallel, Canada is going through a phase of internal political turmoil. The recent announcement of Trudeau's resignation from the leadership of the

Liberal Party and the nomination of Mark Carney as the leader of the same party, has triggered a transition phase, which will culminate in the Canadian federal elections scheduled for October 2025. This internal dynamic highlights how issues of national security and Arctic protection have taken centre stage in the country's political debate. Both the new Prime Minister, Mark Carney,¹⁴¹ and the leader of the Conservative Party, Pierre Poilievre, are focusing on the need to increase defence spending and strengthen Canada's strategic presence in the Arctic.

Although these issues have been the subject of academic analysis and political debate for years, the recent succession of international events has heightened awareness of the looming threats to the Canadian government. In this context, the AFP emerges as an essential response to growing pressures from established hostile actors, such as Russia, and emerging powers with strategic interests in the region, such as

¹³⁸ Mueller, Julia. "What to know about Trump's calls to make Canada the '51st state'", *The Hill*, 8.01.2025

¹³⁹ White House. 'Fact Sheet: President Donald J. Trump Imposed Tariffs on Imports from Canada, Mexico and China', *White House*, 1.02.2025.

¹⁴⁰ Huebert, Rob et. Al.. 'Strategic Outlook', pp. 4-6

¹⁴¹ Lévesque, Catherine. "Mark Carney wins Liberal leadership by a landslide with 86% of votes", *National Post*, 9.03.2025

China. And the need to meet the expectations of historical allies, such as the United States, further complicates the picture.

Although the AFP outlines strategic priorities and accurately describes the current Arctic scenario, it does not provide operational guidance on how to achieve many of Canada's goals, including reaching the 2% of GDP threshold for military spending. The main challenge for Canada therefore remains to translate strategic orientations into concrete actions. The future Canadian government, whatever it may be, will have to ensure continuity in defence investment and effectively resist foreign interference.

Continuity and innovation: Arctic policies compared

After having briefly looked at the strategies contained in the new Arctic Defence Policy, it becomes interesting to analyse the elements of continuity and innovation of the *Arctic Foreign Policy* (2024) compared to the *Arctic and Northern Policy Framework* (2019). This comparison provides a better understanding of the change of pace of Canada's Arctic strategy and its implications for the future of the region.

The two main elements of continuity of the *Arctic Foreign Policy* with respect to the 2019 *Framework* are the focus on climate change issues and the recognition of the importance of *human security* for the peoples of the North to which the goals of integration and growth for indigenous peoples are linked.

In the AFP, the fight against climate change is seen as the most urgent challenge for Canada, not only because of the devastating effects it may cause directly, but also, as mentioned above, because of the geopolitical impacts it may have:

Climate change is both the most pressing and the most proximate threat to Canada's security in the Arctic and the people who live there. Its causes and effects are not bound by countries' official borders. (AFP, 2024)

Even in the ANPF, climate change was already considered a primary threat to be addressed:

Adaptation and resilience-building measures will be required to respond to the climate-driven change happening now, and projected for the future. (ANPF, 2019)

With regard to the goals of integration and growth for indigenous peoples, the *Arctic Foreign Policy* recognises the need to work closely with indigenous communities, involving indigenous leaders in decision-making processes. This approach is evidenced, for example, in the resolution of border disputes, in line with Canada's broader goal of assert-

ing sovereignty while respecting indigenous rights and knowledge systems:

Arctic diplomacy should be informed by and benefit Arctic and northern Indigenous Peoples and other northerners. [...] Grounded in a commitment to reconciliation, this policy seeks to build in the Arctic foreign policy space a renewed Inuit-Crown and nation-to-nation relationship with Indigenous Peoples based on the recognition of rights, respect, cooperation and partnership. (AFP, 2024)

Even in the previous *Framework*, the central position of indigenous communities was recognised throughout the document. In the spirit of the principle '*nothing about us, without us*',¹⁴² participation in discussions of international issues was considered central even then:

Enhance the representation and participation of Arctic and northern Canadians in relevant international

¹⁴² "Nothing about us without us" (Latin: *Nihil de nobis, sine nobis*) is a slogan used to communicate the idea that no policy should be decided by a representative without the full and direct participation of the members of the group or groups affected by that policy. From Lumby, Noe. 'Nothing About us, without us: Reflecting on the failed referendum', *Journal of Global Indigeneity*, 14.10.2024

forums and negotiations. (ANPF, 2019)

On this strategy, the new policy therefore constitutes continuity with the previous one, complementing it with new actions to be undertaken, but following the same goal of protection, growth and active involvement of indigenous peoples in the decision-making process.

The real innovation contained in the AFP, which represents the real step forward compared to pre-existing documents such as the *Framework*, is the Canadian government's recognition of the profound changes in the geopolitical landscape. Canada is, in fact, fully aware of the global impact, with direct consequences also on the Arctic, of the ongoing war in Ukraine and of the fact that Chinese interests in the region go far beyond mere scientific research. And what is most striking is the strong tone in which the government has chosen to express its position. The *Arctic Foreign Policy* does not merely outline the challenges, but sends a clear signal of firmness, hinting at a shift in Canadian attitudes

towards Arctic defence and security.

The main innovative elements in the comparison between the two policies that emerge from this analysis thus seem to be: the theme of sovereignty and defence, the renewed concept of diplomacy and the use of tone towards nations considered hostile such as Russia and China.

As mentioned, on the issue of geopolitical sovereignty and defence there is a marked change of pace, although there are elements of continuity in Canadian aims in the *Arctic Foreign Policy*:

The Government of Canada will continue to take a comprehensive approach to Arctic security by prioritizing the security, interests and priorities of the Arctic region and northerners, as well as Canadians more broadly. (AFP, 2024)

An example of the change of tone concerns the way border dispute resolution issues are addressed. In the ANPF, a collaborative approach is used, without providing clear guidance on how to resolve disputes:

Define more clearly Canada's marine areas and boundaries in the

Arctic [...] seeking appropriate opportunities to resolve outstanding boundary issues. International rules and institutions will play an important role in helping Canada address these issues. (ANPF, 2019)

The AFP addresses territorial disputes with more determination, introducing targeted strategies for border management with Denmark, the definition of the continental shelf and relations with the United States:

At a time when the rules-based international order is under unprecedented threat [...] Canada has made resolving boundary disputes [...] one of the foundational principles of its foreign policy in the Arctic. (AFP, 2024)

Another element of change concerns the concept of diplomacy, AFP reports:

To ensure that the Arctic remains stable, prosperous and secure and to fully implement the objectives laid out in the International chapter of the ANPF, Canada needs a diplomatic strategy that responds to this evolving geopolitical context. (AFP, 2024)

It is clear, therefore, that the concept of multilateral diplomacy

and cooperation described in the *Framework* appears outdated:

Despite increased interest in the region from both Arctic and non-Arctic states, Canada continues to cooperate effectively with international and domestic partners to ensure the Arctic remains a region of peace and stability. (ANPF, 2019)

This approach leaves room for the AFP's 'pragmatic diplomacy':

Reorients Canada's approach to the Arctic based on a clear-eyed assessment of the threats Canada faces today, and those it anticipates in the future. It aligns Canada's foreign and defence policy to ensure the security of Canadians and ensures that together with its allies, Canada can guard against and defend itself against threats from its adversaries in the Arctic. By reinforcing the pillars of Arctic governance and the principles of the rules-based international order, this policy will help to safeguard the collective interests of the peoples of the Arctic from those who would seek to impose their wills. [...] It will produce new and more effective ways of working together on Arctic diplomacy. (AFP, 2024)

Parallel to this strategic change, a change of tone towards Russia,

compared to what was contained in the 2019 *Framework* is evident in the new policy:

We will take steps to restart a regular bilateral dialogue on Arctic issues with Russia in key areas. [...] Such dialogues recognize the common interests, priorities and challenges faced by Canada, Russia and our respective Arctic and Northern communities as they struggle to adapt to and thrive in rapidly changing conditions. (ANPF, 2019)

In the new AFP, Russia is described in decidedly more aggressive tones, an approach never seen in a Canadian document since the end of the Cold War:

Canada has been clear that there will be no business as usual with Russia [...] Canada will not allow Russia to undermine, through its actions, the pillars of international cooperation in the Arctic. [...] Russia represents a generational geopolitical challenge." (AFP, 2024)

The reference to China is a further novelty, not even mentioned in the *Framework*, where 'non-Arctic states' are mentioned in general:

We will also consider establishing Arctic dialogues with key non-Arctic states and actors, where practical, to discuss issues of mutual interest. (ANPF, 2019)

In the AFP, China, given its growing influence in the Arctic, plays a central role and Canada is very hard on Beijing:

China seeks to shape the international order into a more permissive environment for interests and values that increasingly deviate from Canada's commitment to a rules-based international system. China can be expected to use all the tools at its disposal to advance its geopolitical interests, including in the Arctic. Canada will challenge China when it ought to and cooperate when its interests align with China's. (AFP, 2024)

From a comparison of the two policies, the evolution of Canadian policy towards the Arctic in recent years is thus evident, and equally evident is the drastic change with the *Arctic Foreign Policy* of the historical conception of the Arctic as a place of peace and collaboration.

Conclusions

The *Arctic Foreign Policy* of 2024 marks a significant turning point in Canada's Arctic strategy, putting a definitive end to the 'Arctic exceptionalism' that has characterised the region for decades. Historically regarded by Canada as an area of cooperation and stability, the Arctic is now at the centre of global competition between powers such as the United States, Russia and China.

This change has forced Canada to adopt a more realistic approach, focusing on security, sovereignty and the need to strengthen its position through strategic alliances. Although the AFP appears to be more of a strategic orientation document than a detailed operational plan.

Canada, as well as the United States and the European Union, now seem to be fully aware of the growing competition in the Arctic, although the challenges in the region have been evident for years. From this perspective, it is clear that Canada and its Western allies are currently lagging behind

the Sino-Russian front. And while China has only been present in the region for a few years, Russia has long invested heavily in upgrading its military infrastructure and operational capacity in the Arctic, leaving no room for interpretation as to what its intentions are in the region.

The international scenario is evolving towards a form of 'realism',¹⁴³ in which states seek to maximise their own interests at the expense of others, adopting targeted strategies to obtain maximum benefits and moving increasingly away from international cooperation. In this 'neorealist' context, security becomes the main objective of every state. This approach is reflected in the Arctic, where Canada must orient its policy in response to this new global scenario.

The *Arctic Foreign Policy* of 2024 represents a decisive shift in this direction, with an awareness that integrates previous goals, such as the welfare of northern communities and sustainable development with a new integrated strategy, including the strengthening of

¹⁴³ Bell, Duncan, "Neorealism in international relations", *Britannica*, consulted in 2025

defence capabilities and an increased diplomatic presence in the region.

However, this transition is not without its challenges. Canada will have to balance its security policy with the need to maintain a credible commitment to the indigenous peoples, while avoiding a military focus overshadowing efforts at reconciliation and social development. Defence Minister Bill Blair emphasised the importance of the concept of balancing the two:

Arctic Foreign Policy responds to these growing challenges with a focus on asserting our sovereignty in the North, while supporting prosperity for those living there.¹⁴⁴

Looking to the future, Canadian leadership in the Arctic will depend on its ability to transform the AFP into a concrete and effective plan of action. If Canada wants to fulfil its objectives and establish itself as a leader in the region, it will have to increase its hard power and strengthen cooperation with allies. At the same time, it will have to seize the

opportunity to use this new policy as a means to advance the process of reconciliation with indigenous peoples by integrating them more into policy decisions.

The Arctic of the near future will be an increasingly complex area, characterised by geopolitical tensions and unprecedented environmental challenges. Canada has before it the opportunity to consolidate its leading role in the region, but to do so it will have to demonstrate consistency between declarations and actions, investing in security without sacrificing the values of cooperation and inclusion that have historically guided its Arctic policy, and this regardless of who will lead the country in the future.

¹⁴⁴ Government of Canada, "Canada's Arctic Foreign Policy"

